

The Sense of Materiality

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Type of Paper: Case Study

Conference Theme: Space and Environment

Background and Context

This case study focuses on the interior reconstruction of a two storey house in Singapore. Susan Seah and Thomas Kong, partners of SKA Architects were engaged by the client to redesign the interior spaces for living, social entertainment and the display of both his antique Chinese and contemporary furniture collections. In addition, SKA Architects were asked to acknowledge his Chinese roots in the overall ambience of the spaces. The house is a modern version of the traditional shophouse in Singapore. Introduced during the colonial era, the shophouse was originally designed to combine work and living spaces within a building. (Jane, Jane, 1985) The ground level shop opens out to a five foot wide covered walkway that links the units together to form a continuous block facing a common street. It also shelters one from rain and the intense heat and glare of the tropical sun. An air well located at mid point of the interior facilitates natural ventilation in the warm and humid climate and direct light into its deep interiors. The context of the shophouse is an important consideration in this project as the specificity of culture and climate moderated our subsequent design decisions.

Design Intent and Direction

The primary focus of our design is centred on the silent dialogue between the body and material reality, to find appropriate opportunities where quotidian experiences can be heightened and made extraordinary. Materials are investigated and their innate materiality amplified, overlaid and combined to provoke desired ambience and atmosphere. We explore the use of light and shadows, the aural, tactile and visual qualities of materials and how their juxtapositions can draw out emotional responses that engender a multi-sensory poetic experience. For example, the sense of mystery and depth evoked by the withholding and concealing nature of shadows, or one of intensity and focus by combining light with strong colours. These strategies are employed to orchestrate a rich and experiential spatial narrative throughout the interior space.

Threshold

The design conceives of the interior and the exterior as permeable social and experiential thresholds. The sheltered five foot walkway commonly serves as a social space where neighbours can meet and talk. It is not unusual to find this space personalized with outdoor plants or benches, expanding the interior out to the exterior space. The first set of wooden

sliding grilles is retained to continue this social permeability between the public walkway and the private interior. The actual set of doors is set deeper into the house and designed as full height, pivoted and in unfinished steel. By setting back the entrance, we transformed this space into a semi dark interior, in contrast with the bright exterior. The visual acclimatisation is deliberately designed to mark an experiential threshold between the exterior and the interior of the house, one that is characteristic of spaces in the tropics.

Materiality of light and shadow

We explore how the manipulation of natural and artificial light and its effect on a material's surface can transform our perception of materiality and spaces. A continual feature in the house is the full height pivot timber screen doors strategically repeated throughout different parts of the interior. At a cultural level, the screens are abstracted forms used in traditional Chinese architecture. However, its materiality is altered by locating a row of lights on the ceiling along the length of the timber screen doors, which turn its mass and weight into one of delicacy and lightness at night. Visually, the screen doors appear to float off the surface of the wall due to the masking of the timber's materiality as thin, vertical silhouettes. Furthermore, through careful placement and contrast of the reflectivity of materials and furniture, as well as their proximity to windows and light fixtures, we were able to achieve a dramatic sense of focus, depth and mystery, whilst extending visual connectivity between the interior and exterior. In the bed chamber, we deliberately directed the overhead light on the Chinese antique bed to bring this artifact into focus, keeping the surrounding spaces dim to further enhance dramatic and mysterious qualities. Two layers of translucent curtains positioned around the bed offer an additional sense of depth when viewed against the rich colour and lustre of the bed's fabric. The sense of a gentle breeze is reinforced visually in the kitchen through the overlapping, moving patterns of leaves reflected off the steel surfaces of the kitchen cabinets. Similarly, the use of highly polished granite surface for the Jacuzzi visually draws the trees and bamboos outside the house into its interior, evoking an experience of visual expansiveness as one emerges from the dark and narrow staircase.

Tactility of stone and wood

The sense of hardness and firmness as one walks on stone, contrasted with the feeling of coolness and dampness when in contact with water is an experience we have in mind in the

design of the bathroom. We imagine this to be a special place, where the ritual of cleansing can potentially be a pleasurable one. We choose a charcoal gray stone cut into large modular panels to contrast with the intimacy of the contoured body. The panels are used as both floor and wall finishes, creating a continuity of surface and a sense of the body being enclosed all around. We deliberately set up a dialectical relationship between body and material to activate the innate sensibilities of the body when contrasted with a surface or material possessing a very different quality than itself. The softness of flesh becomes intensified when in contact with the hardness of stone. The texture and colour of the stone wall also presented a natural background to bring out the delicate lines and details of the antique and the contemporary furniture. In our choice of wood for the pivot screen doors, we avoided the design of a door handle as we intend the act of opening the door to be an intimate, direct encounter between body and object. The timber poles are therefore dimensioned so that they fit comfortably within the grasp of one's hand.

Water and reflectivity

Water and its associated impressions of coolness and dampness mediate between the sensing body and the enduring firmness of stone in the bathroom. The stone floor is left unpolished to allow water to leave traces, marking the passage of time and offer surfaces that the overhead lights can reflect off. The reflective nature of still water is taken advantage of in other areas where it can be manifested against glass surfaces while contained. During the day, light from the pool reflects off the ceiling and walls that are left unpainted, creating moving and changing patterns that can rouse a dreamlike state of mind. While at night, the reflectivity of glass and water combine to create an illusionistic space beyond the physical boundary of the house.

The aural and springing sensation of steel

The staircase is constructed of unfinished steel bent to form into steps. As one walks on these steps, a low, reverberating sound is experienced. The sound is magnified softly between the timber screen and the masonry wall, which enables one to intuitively sense the difference in scale and volume along this transitional space between the two floors. One also senses a slight bounce when walking on the steps as the steel resisted the weight of the body, thereby allowing the body to be aware of its own presence.

The silent witness of objects

Our strategy for the placement of furniture aims at highlighting their displacement from the original place and time. We wish to bring out a sense of uncanny and quiet tension through their presence, rather than integrating them seamlessly into the interior landscape. Moreover, given the client's persistent absence from the house, the furniture assume the role of solitary, silent witnesses in space. We recall Aldo Rossi's project, the Domestic Theatre, designed for the XVII Milan Triennale in 1986 and featured in Lotus Documents 8 (Teysot, 1987). In this theoretical work, everyday household appliances took on a larger than life presence in the house. Time seemed to stand still, while the reflective vessels visually captured and extended the surrounding environment on their surfaces, albeit in a distorted fashion.

Theoretical Foundation

Our project is based on the theoretical foundation that there is continuity between our body and the built environment. This continuity implies that what we experience external to our body are not mute objects or spaces; but that they possess meanings we can sense, recognise and associate our emotions with. Our project also assumes that experiences are 'lived similarities' to borrow a term from Walter Benjamin (Bullock, Eiland, Jennings, Smith, Eds., 2005). This commonality and continuity is what makes communication of poetic meanings through materials, spaces and forms possible. It is a silent dialogue; one that takes place at both the conscious and sub-conscious level through our everyday encounter with the built and natural world. Robert Vischer, a German philosopher in the nineteenth century and several of his contemporaries speculated on the possibility of an empathic relationship between forms and the physiology of the body and emotions (Vischer, 1873). Their philosophical speculations attempted to give meanings to establish a bridge between the private imagination and creation of the artist with the larger world around him. For Vischer, we can read and feel the subjective play and manipulation of ornaments and mass of an architect because we associate them with our own body. He wrote:

Total regularity occurs only in certain parts of the human body (the eye), and accordingly we like to see it in part of the object...Again, we find that horizontal symmetry always presents a better effect than vertical symmetry because of its analogy with our body (1873: 97-98).

Vischer also reminded us that our perception of the external world is not solely dependent on sight but which involves the entire active sensing body, and that the transference of sensations is possible across senses. He elaborated, "Similarly, we speak of 'loud colours'

because their shrillness does indeed induce an offensive sensation in our auditory nerves. In rooms with low ceilings our whole body feels the sensation of weight and pressure.” (1873: 98) In the section on feeling and emotion, Vischer celebrated an emotional existence that gives thoughtful consideration to others, beyond the confines of one’s own. He wrote:

Only by considering our fellow beings do we ascend true emotional life. This natural love for my species is the only thing that makes it possible for me to project myself mentally; with it, I feel not only myself but at the same time the feeling of another being (1873: 103).

Implications

Robert Vischer’s theory of empathic relationship between the outer world and our inner life as well as the value of a shared and considered emotional existence has significant implications for design. It re-orientates design away from a purely conceptual laden approach, towards one that requires designers to be sensitive to the inflections and nuances of living and to see design as a configuration and intensification of the everyday through care, empathy and generosity. No longer is design concerned with just the endless invention of the new, the uncritical application of technology for visualization and production or the self promotional interests of designers. In the context of designing an interior space or a building, this mode of thinking and working is particularly refreshing and revealing. Whether an architect or interior designer uses the computer, pencil or his/her own bare hands in shaping and forming a work into existence, it is an invitation to participation and to action, both in the private and the collective realm. Architectural and interior design becomes one that is situated in the world and a search for shared aspirations, meanings, emotions and the common good. In the process, it can only deepen our comprehension of the world of things, phenomenon, and human relationships while renewing the pleasure of design.

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Acknowledgment

We wish to thank Raymond Quek for his thoughtful comments and Kheng- Li Wee for the photographs featured in this paper.

Figures

Figure 1. First and basement floor plans showing relationship of building to covered five foot walkway.

Figure 2. Setting back the main set of doors enables the creation of a social and experiential threshold between interior and exterior.

Figure 3. Full height pivot timber screen doors strategically located to create visual continuity and as backdrop for the furniture.

Figure 4. Mass and weight of timber screen doors transformed into one of delicacy and lightness at night through lighting.

Figure 5. Sense of drama, depth and mystery suggested through lighting, contrast of colours and layering of translucent curtains.

Figure 6. The sense of a gentle breeze is reinforced visually in the kitchen through the overlapping, moving patterns of leaves reflected off the steel surfaces of the kitchen cabinets.

Figure 7. Polished granite surface of Jacuzzi visually draws the exterior into the interior, enabling the experience of visual expansiveness as one emerges from the dark and narrow staircase.

Figure 8. Modular panels of charcoal grey stone on walls and floor set up a contrast between the body and antique furniture.

Figure 9. Reflectivity of glass and water combines to create an illusionistic space beyond the physical boundary of the house at night.

Figure 10. Aural and springing sensation evoked by the resistance of the steel staircase against the body.

Figure 11. Placements of antique and contemporary furniture set up a sense of quiet tension within the interior space.